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Qualitative Study on Foreign Aid Intervention on Civil Conflict Intensity and Sustainable Economic Development in West Africa

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Abstract

Civil conflicts and war have become major threats to several local, regional and global economic growth and sustainable development because of their adverse effects on economic growth and development. Several internal strategies have been deployed but yielded no effective outcome hence, this have led to countries in the West Africa to seek for external assistance. A major focus of assistance is the use of foreign funding. This article examined the use of foreign funding in cushioning civil conflicts in West Africa. The study deployed a mixed studies systematic review, which places emphasis on the use of several studies that have deployed different research designs such as quantitative, qualitative, review, among others from searching from the databases of publishers, television websites, and other publications. Also, materials deployed include those within the years 2013 and 2023. In addition, thematic analysis and content analysis were deployed and used to analyse the information and materials obtained for this study from where inference was made from the study. The findings of this article revealed that seeking foreign aid funding could affect civil conflict intensity in West Africa in two ways. The first is that it could pose a negative effect by increasing the intensity of the civil wars due to selfish ambitions and mismanagement of funds released by donors. Second is that, it could also pose positive effect when used effectively to cushion the civil conflicts. Therefore, this study recommended that foreign aid donors should ensure that monitoring strategies such as donor harmonization, alignment with national development strategies with the recipient country, accountability between donors and countries should be put in place to ensure the proper and effective use of such aids received by West Africa.

Keywords: Foreign Funding, Foreign aids, Civil Conflict, Civil Conflict Intensity, West Africa

Introduction

Civil conflicts and war have become major threats to several local, regional and global economic growth and sustainable development. Gyimah-Brempong and Corley (2001) and Hasan (2022); noted that civil conflicts have adverse effects on economic growth and development. According to Doyle and Sambanis (2003); Clément (2005) and the United Nation (2023), noted that from global level, several civil wars have occurred since after the World War II and have claimed approximately 20 million lives and has displaced approximately 67 million. Also, in West Africa, for several decades, nations in Africa have been affected by various conflicts and civil strife accompanying with high intensity of violence and persistent killings. This has raised major challenges in several West African countries such as Mali, Côte d'Ivoire, Liberia and Sierra Leone, Niger, Ghana, Nigeria, Mauritania, among others (Annan, 2014). In addition, approximately 20 countries in sub-Saharan Africa have experienced at least a period of civil war after their independence and this is even grave and intensified for some countries such as Angola, Sudan, Nigeria, among others. In recent times, the incidence of civil conflict has intensified (Annan, 2014; Stockholm International Peace Research Institute (SIPRI) Yearbook, 2000; Clément, 2005; United Nation, 2023).

Several studies such as Keili (2008); Voz di Paz and Interpeace (2010); Vinck et al (2011); Annan (2014); Amnesty international (2021); among other have noted that civil conflicts in West Africa have been intensified and fuelled by several factors such as the high rate of poverty, human rights violations, bad governance, corruption, ethnic marginalization, among others. A number of factors have been identified as relevant in explaining civil wars in Africa. These factors include the historical legacies of slave trade and colonialism, the nature of the African state after independence, external intervention in the internal affairs of African countries, human rights abuses by African governments, and ethnic and religious grievances. The economic theory of civil war, however, sees civil wars in Africa as being caused by poor growth, poverty, and the abundance of natural resources such as diamonds, gold, and other precious minerals that can often be the source of much greed. Clément (2005) and United Nation (2023) revealed that civil conflict is development in reverse because it has reversal effects on economic development of a nation. This civil conflict related issue is much grave in developing countries such as those in West Africa. Collier and Hoeffler (2002); Clément (2005); United Nation (2023); among others, also revealed that civil conflicts

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reflect both a problem for development and also a failure of development. Also, several studies such as Usman and Mathew (2014); Audu, Lukman and Nyah (2014); Ebeh (2015); Olanrewaju, Folarin and Folarin (2017); Mou and Mou (2017); Akinade(2018); among others have argued that a civil conflicts challenge could pose significant negative effect on sustainable development. Therefore, it affects the three-dimensional variables of sustainable development: economic, social and environmental as stated by United Nation's ESCAP (2015).

What constitute civil conflict could be difficult to explain, because it is frequently difficult to differentiate between the beginning and the end of a conflict period. Every conflict might not be the same because they have different causes, of different intensity, have different geographical spread, and have different duration (Cramer, 1999; Fang, Kothari, McLoughlin &Yenice, 2021). The consequences and the effect of civil conflict in West Africa have led to countries in the region to seek for external assistance because all internal strategies have not yielded effective outcome (Olufemi, 2015; Epron, 2019). According to Obi (2015) and Nwagboso (2018) civil conflict challenges are handled with lukewarm attitude in Africa and this has led to the distortion of structural development. To this end, African countries seek for external foreign aids to help cushion the civil conflict intensity in Africa (Nielsen et al., 2011). Svensson (2019) maintained that several economies, which include African economies, rely heavily on foreign aid, and this has led to a high dependency state for the country. Although, several other studies have argued that such foreign aid dependency could pose negative influence on countries and the region of Africa development. This school of thought is premised on the fact that, according to United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (2007); Omiunu (2012) and Adeoye &Iwegbu (2020), development that lasts is those that rely, harness and deploy the resources within towards achieving development goals.

Africa is the only continent where reliance on official aid inflow outstriped private capital inflow with a large margin and this has constituted a problematic global scenario because, from global perspective, there is no country that has really achieved substantial development relying foreign aid (Melesse, 2021). Focusing on and deploying domestic resources can assist African nations to achieve long term sustainable and higher economic growth and development and will also help them to reduce the problem of overdependence on foreign donor funding couple with the rules that apply to it (United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, 2007; Melesse, 2021). According to Melesse (2021), foreign aid as a practice has failed to achieve poverty reduction targets in Africa.

Despite this, many African countries still seek for foreign aids to handle civil crisis and towards ensuring internal development (Melesse, 2021). The significant positive and negative effect of foreign aid reliance has two sides of the coin in its debate especially in Africa (Melesse, 2021). The first, is that this model provides free money, which in the long run, prevents several African countries from taking the various global and development advantage of opportunities provided through the global economy. Second, is that, this foreign aid may not be seen as an economic problem, but in most occasions, it is the misallocation of these resources, the corruption that covers these misallocations of resources, and in extension bad governance have in one way or the other limit the ability of Africa countries to judiciously use those aid hence, it failed to achieve the major goals and objectives for which they were obtained. To this end, in 2005, the Paris Declaration on Aid Effectiveness has noted the need for several effective monitoring strategies such as donor harmonization, alignment with national development strategies with the recipient country, accountability between donors and countries to at least increase the positive impact of such collected aid (Izobo, 2020).

Foreign aid is ineffective in nations with bad governance and it is unnecessary in nations with good governance. Therefore, sourcing for foreign funding towards ameliorating civil conflict intensity in West Africa may pose a confusing debate. This could be why Melesse (2021) admonished that foreign aid as a practice has failed to achieve poverty reduction targets in Africa hence, has not yielded its objective. However, the continued reliance on foreign aids in West African countries continue to present the need for understanding whether it is still of benefits despite its significant and potential odds to development towards alleviating civil conflicts in the region. Hence, it is important to further examine how the reliance and deployment of foreign funding could assist in cushioning the several civil conflicts in West Africa- this is a major focus of this present paper.

West Africa has recorded several large-scale civil wars and at least seven other conflicts that are more of localized unrest (M'Cormack 2011). Examples of these large-scale civil war are the Biafran War which occurred between 1967 and 1970 in Nigeria, the Liberia civil war which occurred between 1989 and 1996 and also 1999 to 2003), the Sierra Leone civil war which happened between the year 1991 and 2002, the civil war in Guinea-Bissau between 1998 and 1999, civil war in Côte d'Ivoire between 2002 and 2007 and also resurfaced between 2010 and 2011; among others. Marc et al. (2015) revealed selected conflicts in West Africa presented in Table 1.

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Table 1: Selected Conflicts in West Africa to 2012

Name of conflict	Country	Years	Nature of conflict	Estimated fatalities
Guinea-Bissau War of Independence	Guinea-Bissau	1962–74	Insurgency	15,000
Biafran War	Nigeria	1967–70	Civil war	500,000–2,000,000
Casamance conflict	Senegal	1982–present	Insurgency	5,000
Mauritania and Senegal War	Mauritania and Senegal	1989–90	International conflict	500
First Liberian Civil War	Liberia	1989–96	Civil war	100,000–220,000
Tuareg rebellion	Mali	1990–95	Insurgency	—
Sierra Leone Civil War	Sierra Leone	1991–2002	Civil war	50,000–300,000
Guinea-Bissau Civil War	Guinea-Bissau	1998–99	Civil war	655
Second Liberian Civil War	Liberia	1999–2003	Civil war	150,000–300,000
First Ivorian Civil War	Côte d'Ivoire	2002–07	Civil war	3,000
Niger Delta conflict	Nigeria	2004–09	Insurgency	2,500–4,000
Tuareg rebellion	Niger	2007–09	Insurgency	270–400
Boko Haram uprising	Nigeria	2009–present	Insurgency	11,200
Second Ivorian Civil War	Côte d'Ivoire	2010–11	Civil war	3,000
Conflict in Northern Mali	Mali	2012–13	Insurgency	1,270

Source: Data on fatalities are derived from various sources, including Marshall 2005; ACLED 2014; Human Rights Watch 2011b; Nigeria Social Violence Dataset 2014; and Reuters 2009.
Note: — = not available.

Source: Marc et al. (2015)

The impacts of these claimed several lives as revealed in Table 1 above. The impact of these civil war on the civilian population was grave, generating a high number of refugees and internally displaced persons (IDPs) (Luckham and others 2001; Hasan, 2022; United Nation, 2023). There were also much of sexual and gender-based violence against both men and women leading to increased psychological and physiological trauma in the society affected with significant high economic and social costs of the wars on the societies of Liberia, Sierra Leone, among others (Marc et al., 2015). Also, Nigeria has suffered from various overlapping and different forms of political, communal, ethno-religious, election-related, and strives that occurred due to resource allocation and distribution, among others which has also affected the society (Marc et al., 2015). To this end, various strategies have been deployed and sought for towards ensuring that such civil conflicts and unrest are abated to the barest minimum which could include both the internal and external sourcing. Grady (2017), noted that the yearning to [prevent such conflicts and violence has been one of the priorities of the provision of foreign aid which involves given out hundreds of billions of dollars annually which have been expected to be spent on several suggested aid programs towards the decreasing of such civil conflicts. From the actual form of it, such external aid supports and programs should be directed to decrease civil conflicts due to its positive impact on the lives of the beneficiaries within the society of the country of recipient. However, foreign aid supports on civil conflicts have proven frustratingly difficult. This is because in most areas where such aids have been provided especially in West Africa, various and several other problems have made such societies to even have more aggressive civil conflicts due to the inappropriate dissemination of such financial foreign aids (Grady, 2017). Hence, such aid programs fail to achieve their aims and objectives thereby increasing the rate of civil conflicts in many societies in Africa.

Nevertheless, there is the positive aspect of foreign aid support to West African countries. For example, several other studies such (Collier & Hoeffler, 2002; Ree & Nillesen, 2009; Savun & Tirone, 2012; Grady, 2017; Melesse, 2021; Izobo, 2020; among others) also argued that foreign aid could exert a decreasing effect on civil conflicts or war in West Africa. These studies further argued that such foreign aid programs could empower the governments by deploying and using such foreign aid to support domestic expenditures, which could eventually free up other domestic revenue source to increase the local military capacity which could eventually decrease armed rebellion opportunities and could also deter further civil conflict or wars.

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Objective of the Study

The study focuses on examining foreign aid intervention on civil conflict intensity and sustainable economic development in West Africa. The specific objectives are to:

1. Examine foreign aid intervention and how it affects civil conflict intensity and sustainable economic development in West Africa.
2. Ascertain the influence of foreign aid intervention on civil conflict intensity towards enhancing sustainable economic development in West Africa

Research Question

The following research question was used to drive this study:

1. How does foreign aid intervention affect civil conflict intensity in West Africa?
2. How does the influence of foreign aid intervention on civil conflict intensity affect sustainable economic development in West Africa?

Methodology

The study deployed a mixed studies systematic review, which places emphasis on the use of several studies that have deployed different research designs such as quantitative, qualitative, review, among others. A systematic review strategy focuses on using systematic methods to collect and appraise data and information obtained from secondary sources or studies which could include searching from the databases of publishers, television websites, and other publications. It is designed to enumerate and provide a complete and exhaustive summary of current evidence (Giang et al., 2019) which in this study focus on fighting for Aid: deploying foreign funding to cushion civil conflict intensity in West Africa. In addition, the major search engines used to search for materials in this study are the google scholar and the google search engines. The Cochrane reviews style was deployed and used in this study for the reviewing of the literature as stated by Sieving (2007) and Chapman (2014). Also, the PICOS framework was used to inform the search strategy (Huang et al., 2006) as represented by Richardson (1995): P – Problem or Population; I – Intervention; C – Comparison, control or comparator; O – Outcome(s); S – Study.

With regards to this study, the PICOS framework used is presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. PICOS

	Inclusion	Exclusion	Search terms
Problem and Population Intervention	Civil conflict intensity in West African Countries Foreign funding	Other national issues Other sources which could include internal sources	Civil conflict intensity in West Africa Foreign funding Aids
Comparator Outcome	None Cushioning Civil conflict intensity	None	None Strategies to cushioning Civil conflict intensity
Study type	Mixed studies systematic review	None	Mixed studies systematic review

The initiation of searching process commenced April 12, 2022 and this was also repeated on May 2-4, 2022 so as to obtain wide relevant resources that have not been previously covered in the previous search especially in the process of writing of and also reviewing the paper. Mixed studies were all considered and adopted in this study and materials deployed include those within the years 2000 and 2021. Also, the PRISMA Flow Diagram for the study search is provided in Figure 1 below.

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Figure 1: The PRISMA Flow Diagram for the Study

To ensure effective materials appraisal in this study, several components were inculcated such as the evaluation of the appropriateness of the study design that was used in the study, the methodological features of such design, the author of the article; sources of the articles, among others. Moreover, to further synthesize the information retrieved, data extraction was deployed but this was revolved around the research aim of the study as stated by Frederiksen (2017). In addition, thematic analysis and content analysis were deployed and used to analyse the information and materials obtained for this study from where inference was made from the study.

Empirical Results and Discussion

The study focused on examining the impact of foreign aid funding on civil conflict intensity in West Africa, and it is divided into two major sections based on the research questions of the article.

Research Question 1

How does foreign aid intervention affect civil conflict intensity in West Africa?

Mousseau (2021) did a study on whether foreign development aid trigger ethnic war in developing states, and revealed that higher availability of foreign development aid could exacerbate the propensity for ethnic war. This implies that foreign aid could play major role in stimulating ethnic violence in countries such as West Africa hence, it posed negative impact on the probability for a civil conflict. However, increasing aid flow could decrease the duration of conflict. Hence, foreign aid flows could be an important tool for policymakers and aid agencies towards the prevention of future civil wars especially in West Africa.

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Annan (2014) examined the violent conflicts and civil strife in West Africa: causes, challenges and prospects, through a review study, stated that ending violent conflicts and civil strife in West Africa requires the collaboration and collection of various efforts which could also include those related to foreign aid funding towards the

1. Identification of the causal factors of conflicts;
2. Development of concrete strategies and also programmes that could be directed towards the prevention, management and totally resolving the various conflicts;
3. The documentation, management and disseminating of information on the various lessons learnt and best practices of conflict prevention and resolution towards ensuring effective peace building across West Africa
4. Harnessing the indigenous conflict prevention mechanisms while trying to leverage on other contemporary advanced mechanisms so as to adequately address the present and emerging insecurities and violent conflicts in West Africa.

The study of Annan (2014) revealed that to an extent, foreign aid funding support could be useful when it is deployed to ensure that civil conflicts for which it was obtained for are addressed to the barest minimum to attain and achieve peacebuilding across West Africa. Mousseau (2021) examined whether foreign development aid trigger civil war in developing states, and the findings revealed that foreign aid could trigger society imbalance which could increase the risk of civil war. This supports the arguments that foreign aid can exacerbate tensions and cause division in the societies, leading the marginalized populations of the society to rebel. Hence, foreign aid plays a significant role in the stimulation of society violence such as civil conflicts. Although, foreign aid has an inherent designed that should be directed to improve stability within the state, but the disbursement of foreign aids does not guarantee peace but rather could be a cause of civil conflicts. Foreign aid donors should pay emphasis on the differences on domestic politics while trying to formulate and provide aid packages to the various developing countries for assistance. This could be used to justify the work of United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (2007); Svensson (2019); Adeoye and Iwegbu (2020); and Melesse (2021), that economies such as African economies rely heavily on foreign aid which has led to high dependency state for countries. However, Annan (2014) noted that West African Countries have rich indigenous cultural and social values such as respect, protection of human life, freedom, cooperation and tolerance; consists of diverse population and various civil society organizations that should and could harnessed as prospective and major strengths that could be used as driving force to cushion the various violent conflicts and civil strife in West Africa.

Research Question 2

How does the influence of foreign aid intervention on civil conflict intensity affect sustainable economic development in West Africa?

Drawing inference from the study of Annan (2014), that to an extent, foreign aid funding support could be useful to achieve peacebuilding, it could be deduced that this could include sustainable economic development across West Africa. Also, Izobo (2020) investigated the Impact of foreign aid in Africa: a case study of Botswana and Somalia and found that despite donors' original intentions for the distribution of aid, the high levels of corruption in Africa within recipient governments couple with poor democratic institutions, difficult conditions attached to the aids, fiscal imprudence from the recipients are major factors that have changed the original intention of foreign aid from blessing to a curse rather in several African countries. This implies that, such foreign aids could enhance sustainable, bur for the prevalence of corruption, it could impede sustainable economic development in West Africa. To cushion this, there is need to curtail directing foreign aid to countries that lack strong democratic institutions, and various economic sanctions should be used to monitor and motivate governments and political elites into political and economic reforms towards enhancing the effective use of such foreign aids. Such could constitute an effective aid conditionality that could be deployed to improve the chances of political and economic development. Hence, justifying the assertion of Omiunu (2012), that countries such as the West African Countries should focus on local and indigenous resources as another option for cushioning civil wars and conflicts in West Africa.

Izobo (2020) maintained that however, foreign aid supports enable African governments to strengthen local institutions through the provision of educational and technical support. Also, foreign aid can improve governance and also respect for the rule of law through the reduction in corruption be the effective management of expenditure and revenue creation for a country. Nevertheless, foreign aid can also pose significant impact by also challenging the rule of law and democratic reforms. For example, in an autocratic government, foreign aids can be used by such autocratic government by creating larger pool of resources officials and political elites in the government circle which they can fight on and also used for selfish and personal gains, this, in the long run may be detrimental to the country. Hence, civil conflicts, political instability, among others

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that have occurred in Africa over the past five decades could be as a result of the misappropriation of foreign aid received. Izobo (2020) further revealed that when countries are exposed to higher levels of foreign aid, it could destroy the quality of national and regional governance, hence, affect sustainable economic development. For example, the political in African countries have little or no motivation for acquiring such reform, they only use such accrued fund for selfish ambition such as salary increments, luxurious vehicles and houses, among others. This implies that, foreign aids could pose a positive and negative impact on African countries depending on the government and the environment of the nation that is whether it operates a corrupt economy or not.

Also, Grady (2017) examined aid for peace: does foreign aid deter violence, and found that foreign aid is associated with a little increase in violence, but this is only true when the aid programs and support are not provided on a continuous basis in future years. Also, it was revealed by Grady (2017) that there are two primary mechanisms that are used to justify the negative impact of foreign aids as it tends to increase conflicts and include from the political and economic effects. With regards to politics, there could be constant pressure for elections and the involvement of multiparty democracy without previous and future political development giving room for the deployment of ethnicity as a primary tool for mobilization especially among the elites that seek the public votes. Also, from the economic aspect, foreign aids release and give resources to the deprived areas of a society, and this may often lead to the neglect of inequality thereby neglecting some other ethnic groups within that society hence the existence and prevalence of biased resource allocation. Therefore, foreign aids could heighten the propensity of civil war in a given African society due to the fact that it has the tendency to increase the financial value within the state and also to lead to rebel that could cause civil conflicts. The following are several aspects provided by Grady (2017) that foreign aids could increase civil wars:

1. By adding resources to ongoing conflict, foreign aid could fuel civil crisis especially if such aid resources are distributed to the conflict actors which could occur via poor oversight, particularly when it is hard to track the resources.
2. By increasing the value of the zero-sum resources, foreign aid, focuses at increasing the value of an area's resources. In the case where the increased resources fail to reach the hands of active or potential conflict actors, the increase in the value of something will definitely increase the demand for such. For example, if there is an agricultural aid which could tend to increase land productivity, individuals may fight to possess more land or try as much as possible to defend their land.
3. By destabilizing the local economies leading to economic volatility. For example, economies that tend to rely on foreign aids tend to be more volatile than economies that do not because such allocations of aid could change year-in-year-out than the domestic production. This could further affect national governments and the local areas because local national workers would tend to develop skills necessary to gain employment into the aid organizations thereby leaving out other skill or local skills that are identified with the local environment of the nation. Such process may drain the local indigenous value of the nation in the long run.
4. By mismanagement of foreign aids. Aid provided to local environment could be mismanaged or poorly managed thereby increasing the civil conflicts or war tension again due to the mismanagement of the foreign aid resources disseminated to the local environment.

This justifies the findings of Melesse (2021) that foreign aid has actually failed to achieve poverty reduction targets in Africa. Also, Grady (2017) noted that foreign aids could reduce civil wars through the following:

1. Peace & Security aid aims at changing attitudes towards crisis or war and changing attitudes towards the potential targets of crisis or war, and also teaching about conflict resolution skills that could help cushion the civil crisis or war.
2. It could lead to economic increase because crisis or war is said to be caused by material deprivation and the resulting personal desperation. Hence, economic aid tends to indirectly affect crisis or war by the improvement of material lives of the aid recipients' nation. Hence, this could decrease the propensity to for the people to perpetrate crisis or war.
3. Result in democracy & Governance effect because politics is often used to mobilize societal cleavages, hence, such aids could be deployed to decrease civil crisis or war. This is because an inclusive electoral system tends to diminish civil crisis or war tendency through the decreasing of political grievances. It could also aid then decrease in likelihood a candidate feels the election was rigged. It could make the polling stations secure, thereby decreasing the propensity to intimidate voters.
4. Leads to better education through the same indirect mechanisms as it does in the economic and Peace & Security. Hence, increasing education tends to increase economic opportunities that could tend to remove incentives that are deployed to perpetrate violence.
5. Increases Health that could reduce such civil wars because poor health is often the cause of terrible material realities and much poverty and desperation.

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This finding concurs with the works of Collier & Hoeffler (2002); Ree & Nillesen (2009); Savun & Tirone (2012); Grady (2017); among others that foreign aid could exert a decreasing effect on civil conflicts or war in West Africa

Conclusion

In conclusion, foreign aid funding could have a two side of coin to affecting civil conflict intensity in West Africa. The first is that it could pose a negative effect by increasing the intensity of the civil wars due to selfish ambitions and mismanagement of funds released by donors. Second is that it could also pose positive effect when used effectively to cushion the civil conflicts.

Recommendations

Therefore, this study recommended that:

1. Foreign aid donors should ensure that monitoring strategies such as donor harmonization, alignment with national development strategies with the recipient country, accountability between donors and countries should be put in place to ensure the proper and effective use of such aids received in West Africa.
2. Donor of foreign aids should also endeavour to see to it that recipient countries have proper and accountable governance system following previous pattern of fund allocation.
3. Also, donor of foreign aids to West African countries should support research that seeks to search into the population of West African countries to investigate how government use funds, even local funds to meet local and the population needs. This could be used to know which country can have access to such foreign aids towards supporting them to cushion conflicts in their societies.

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